

Webis at Sim4IA 2025: Prediction of Next User Queries as a Sequence-To-Sequence Problem

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Abstract

We describe the Webis Group’s runs submitted to the two subtasks A1 and A2 of the micro-shared task on user simulation for ad hoc retrieval systems at the Sim4IA Workshop 2025. For our runs, we model next query prediction as a sequence-to-sequence problem and train variants of a local GPT-2-based query predictor for both subtasks. In addition, we have also submitted two manual runs in which two IR researchers attempt to predict the next query of a search session while being allowed to use any tools they like (e.g., commercial search engines or translation services)—this way, these two runs basically manually “simulate” automatic user simulation.

Keywords

user simulation, ad hoc retrieval, sequence-to-sequence modeling

1. Introduction

Before the advent of the transformer architecture, user simulation for the evaluation of ad hoc and conversational information retrieval systems has been mainly rule- or Markov model-based and in essence had remained more of a theoretical idea [1]. However, with the progressing accessibility and effectiveness of large language models (LLMs), LLM-based user simulation has been explored in the context of evaluating ad hoc retrieval systems [2, 3], but also conversational search [4, 5, 6, 7] and recommender systems [8, 9, 10] with most studies indicating a promising potential of LLM-based user simulation in IR evaluation; with the topic’s popularity further emphasized through a variety of past and upcoming workshops and shared tasks around user simulation [11, 12, 13].

With our contribution to the two subtasks A1 and A2 of the micro-shared task on user simulation at the Sim4IA Workshop 2025, we want to investigate an queries-only sequence-to-sequence approach to predicting the next search query in a given search session (i.e., given a sequence of previous queries, output a sequence of plausible next queries in the same session). Even though most existing user simulation approaches for ad hoc retrieval exploit meta information (e.g., shown search results) or interaction information (e.g., clicks), in some scenarios these are not available so that we trained three variants of simulators using a local GPT-2 model [14] that only know the previous query and then predict the next one—these runs were submitted to subtask A1 (predicting the next query based on a single previous query) as well as to subtask A2 (predicting the next query based on a whole previous session). As for subtask A2, we also submitted two manual runs in which two IR researchers were allowed to look at the whole previous session and to use any tools they liked (e.g., search results or query suggestions of commercial search engines such as Google or Google Scholar; translation services; etc.) to predict the next query—kind of a manual “simulation” of automatic user simulation.

Sim4IA'25: SIGIR 2025 Second Workshop on Simulations for Information Access

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Table 1

Number of queries and sessions from the different datasets that are used to train our next-query-prediction models before and after applying filter heuristics.

Dataset	All		Filtered	
	Queries	Sessions	Queries	Sessions
Archive Query Log	51,298,196	–	13,390,050	–
<i>dblp.org</i>	5,762,062	–	3,059,788	–
<i>google.com</i>	20,023,180	–	5,227,488	–
<i>scholar.google.com</i>	25,512,954	–	5,102,774	–
AOL Query Log	16,946,938	657,426	446,608	63,119
Sim4IA Training Set	176	45	176	45

2. Next Query Prediction Approaches

In total, we submitted three runs to task A1 and five runs to task A2 including three automatic and two manual runs.

2.1. Automatic Approach

To train our next-query-prediction models, we follow common methodology for training decoder-only large language models (LLMs) which includes a multi-stage training procedure: pretraining, instruction-tuning, and task-specific fine-tuning. The training objective for the pretraining is to learn the query language of keyword queries which differ syntactically from natural language texts that LLMs are usually trained on. After the pretraining, the model could be employed as a query expansion model. In the instruction-tuning step, we shift the training objective to next query prediction, by learning sequences of queries separated by a new special token. For example, an input sequence of consecutive queries “smoking” and “causes from smoking” from the same search session is encoded like `<|bos|>smoking<|sep|>causes from smoking<|eos|>`. This approach has the advantage that multiple consecutive future queries can be predicted until the end-of-sequence token is reached. Finally, in the fine-tuning step we use the provided training set of the Sim4IA shared task to adapt to the task-domain of scientific retrieval.

Due to hardware limitations, we apply the training procedure to reasonably small base models, such that we are able to do weight updates in all layers of the LLM. That way we avoid training adapter matrices like low-rank adaptation (LoRA) [15] instead of training the actual model weights. Therefore, we use GPT-2 [14] as a base model in two different sizes: base with 137 million and medium with 380 million parameters.

Training Data and Preprocessing As mentioned above, we follow a three stage training procedure consisting of pretraining, instruction-tuning, and fine-tuning. For pretraining, we use queries from the Archive Query Log [16] that were issued to *dblp.org*, *google.com*, and *scholar.google.com* which sum up to about 50 million queries (see Table 1 for reference). We excluded queries that contained more than two full stops, were longer than ten query terms, or were not in English language which reduced the number of queries to about 14 million. For the instruction-tuning, we used the AOL query log¹ since it contains session information. We excluded queries from the sessions that are non-unique or just consist of an url and finally removed search sessions that remained with one query. After applying filter heuristics, we obtained a training set of about 60,000 sessions with about 450,000 queries. Finally, the fine-tuning was done with the training set of the Sim4IA shared task.

¹https://web.archive.org/web/20130609163138/http://www.cim.mcgill.ca/~dudek/206/Logs/AOL-user-ct-collection/U500k_README.txt

Decoding Although our approach is capable of generating multiple future queries based on a past search session of a user, for the shared task we only used the immediate next query until the next separator token is reached. As a decoding strategy, we used diverse beam search [17] with 10 beams to produce our top-10 queries. From those, we excluded non-unique queries.

2.2. Manual Approach

Two researchers from the domain of information retrieval attempted to simulate the search behaviour of the user that issued the queries in the test data while being allowed to use any tool they like. IR researcher 1 followed the strategy of submitting the query to Google or Google Scholar and extracting keyword phrases that seemed related. IR researcher 2 entered the query to Google and extracted queries from Google’s suggestions. If Google didn’t suggest a fitting query the query was shortened and entered in the search box again to obtain a new set of suggestions.

2.3. Overview of Runs

- `webis-qpt2`: GPT-2 as base model, pretrained on the Archive Query Log, instruction-tuned on the AOL query log, fine-tuned on the Sim4IA training set, decoded with diverse beam search.
- `webis-qpt2-medium`: GPT-2 medium as base model, pretrained on the Archive Query Log, instruction-tuned on the AOL query log, fine-tuned on the Sim4IA training set, decoded with diverse beam search.
- `webis-gpt2`: GPT-2 as base model, without the query pretraining stage, instruction-tuned on the AOL query log, fine-tuned on the Sim4IA training set, decoded with diverse beam search.
- `webis-expert-manual1`: IR researcher 1, who issued queries to Google and Google Scholar and extracted keyphrases.
- `webis-expert-manual2`: IR researcher 2, who made use of Google’s query suggestions.

3. Future Evaluation in Interactive Retrieval

We are convinced that user simulation will play a major role for the evaluation of information retrieval in the future. Simulation technology will continue to improve and become an essential tool for developers of information retrieval systems. However, the next important step towards such a future is the development of suitable metrics and methods to reliably quantify the authenticity of the simulated user behaviour. We assume that the validation of user simulations will continue to require experiments with real users for a long time to come, until standardized suites of user simulators are available that are capable of emulating a broad spectrum of search behavior of different real users of cross-domain and cross-system applications.

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